

Association between pre-operative hyperuricemia and risk of in-hospital death in high-risk patients undergoing cardiac surgery An international prospective 14-centre study

David Nagore, Manuel Murie-Fernandez, Jorge M. Nuñez-Cordoba, and Marc Vives on behalf of the Spanish Perioperative Cardiac Surgery Research Group

The detection of relevant risk factors and the understanding of their interactions are crucial for a proper characterisation of cardiac surgery patients preoperatively. This is of great utility for surgical planning and optimising peri-operative care and prevention.¹ Hyperuricemia has gained growing interest as an indicator with potential prognostic value for deleterious short-term events, such as in-hospital death^{2,3} or the requirement of renal replacement therapy (RRT).³ Accumulating evidence further suggests potential differential effects of hyperuricemia according to sex, leading to controversial findings.^{4–7} However, these associations remain insufficiently explored in the high-risk cardiac surgery setting.

To bridge this knowledge gap, we prospectively evaluated the associations of pre-operative hyperuricemia with in-hospital mortality and the need for de novo RRT in a multi-centre cohort of high-risk patients undergoing cardiac surgery. Additionally, we analysed these associations in more detail, considering the possibility of an effect modification by sex. The conclusions of our study could help to improve the prediction capacity of current clinical scores and to optimise the planning of cardiac surgeries.